

EXTRACTION, PHYTOCHEMICALS ANALYSIS AND ANTI-EPILEPTIC ACTIVITY OF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *LITSEA MONOPETALA*

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Abstract

The present study was aimed at evaluating the extraction, phytochemical constituents, and antiepileptic activity of the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala*. The ethanolic extract showed a percentage yield of 12.5% w/w, indicating efficient extraction of bioactive compounds. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of glycosides, flavonoids, phenolics, proteins, carbohydrates, saponins, and tannins. Quantitative estimation showed total flavonoid content of 0.96 mg/100 mg and total phenolic content of 0.75 mg/100 mg, suggesting significant antioxidant potential. The antiepileptic activity was evaluated using pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced and maximal electroshock (MES)-induced seizure models. In the PTZ model, the extract exhibited a dose-dependent increase in seizure onset time and provided up to 70% protection at 200 mg/kg. In the MES model, the extract showed significant protection (70–75%) against seizures, comparable to standard drugs. The results were statistically significant, indicating effective anticonvulsant activity. The observed antiepileptic effect may be attributed to the presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which possess neuroprotective and antioxidant properties. The study concludes that the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* has promising antiepileptic potential and may serve as a natural therapeutic agent for the management of epilepsy.

Keywords: *Litsea monopetala*, Antiepileptic activity, Pentylenetetrazole (PTZ), Maximal electroshock (MES), Phytochemical screening, Flavonoids, Phenolic compounds, Ethanolic extract, Anticonvulsant, Herbal medicine

Introduction

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological disorder characterized by recurrent, unprovoked seizures resulting from abnormal electrical activity in the brain. It affects millions of people worldwide and significantly impairs quality of life ^[1]. Despite the availability of several antiepileptic drugs, their long-term use is often associated with adverse effects, drug resistance, and limited efficacy

in certain patients. Therefore, there is a growing need to explore safer and more effective alternatives, particularly from natural sources [2].

Medicinal plants have been widely investigated for their potential in the management of neurological disorders due to the presence of diverse bioactive phytoconstituents. Compounds such as flavonoids, alkaloids, phenolics, and terpenoids are known to exhibit neuroprotective, antioxidant, and anticonvulsant activities^[3]. These phytochemicals may modulate neurotransmitter systems, reduce oxidative stress, and stabilize neuronal membranes, thereby contributing to antiepileptic effects^[3].

Litsea monopetala, belonging to the family Lauraceae, is a medicinal plant traditionally used in various systems of medicine for its therapeutic properties. It is distributed widely in tropical and subtropical regions and has been reported to possess several pharmacological activities, including anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant, and central nervous system (CNS) depressant effects. The plant is rich in bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and essential oils, which are believed to contribute to its medicinal potential^[4].

Extraction of plant material using suitable solvents plays a crucial role in isolating these bioactive constituents. Ethanol is commonly used as an extraction solvent due to its ability to dissolve a wide range of polar and semi-polar compounds. Phytochemical analysis of the extract provides essential information regarding the presence of active constituents responsible for pharmacological activity^[5-6].

The evaluation of antiepileptic activity using experimental animal models, such as maximal electroshock (MES) and pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced seizure models, is widely accepted for screening potential anticonvulsant agents. These models help in understanding the mechanism of action and efficacy of plant extracts in controlling seizure activity.

In this context, the present study aims to investigate the extraction, phytochemical analysis, and antiepileptic activity of the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala*. The findings of this study may contribute to the development of a novel plant-based therapeutic agent for the effective management of epilepsy with reduced side effects.

Material and Methods

Material

Litsea monopetala leaves were collected and authenticated for the study. Ethanol was used as the solvent for extraction. Pentylenetetrazole (PTZ) and phenytoin were used for inducing and

evaluating seizures in experimental models. Standard laboratory reagents such as Mayer's reagent, ferric chloride, Fehling's solution, and other analytical-grade chemicals were used for phytochemical screening and biochemical analysis. All chemicals used were of analytical grade and obtained from standard sources.

Methods

Extraction by maceration process

Following procedure was adopted for the preparation of extract from the shade dried and powdered herbs. Leaves of *Litsea monopetala* were shade dried at room temperature. 50 gram dried plant material was coarsely powdered and subjected to extraction with petroleum ether by maceration. The extraction was continued till the defatting of the material had taken place. Defatted dried powdered of *Litsea monopetala* has been extracted with ethanol solvent using maceration process for 48 hrs, filtered and dried using vacuum evaporator at 40°C^[7].

Determination of percentage yield

The extraction yield is evaluate of the solvent's efficiency to extracts bioactive components from the selected natural plant samples and it was defined as quantity of plant extracts recovered in mass after solvent extraction compared with the initial quantity of plant samples. After extraction, yield of the plant extracts obtained were calculated in grams and then converted it into percentage ^[8]. The percentage yield of each extract was calculated by using following formula:

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Weight of Extract}}{\text{Weight of powdered drug}} \times 100$$

Phytochemical screening

Phytochemicals encompass a wide range of chemical classes, including alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, phenolic compounds, glycosides, and many others. Each class of phytochemicals may have specific physiological effects and potential health benefits. For example, flavonoids are known for their antioxidant properties, alkaloids often possess antimicrobial or analgesic properties, while terpenoids can have antitumor or anti-inflammatory effects. Phytochemical examinations were carried out for all the extracts as per the standard methods ^[9-10].

Estimation of total flavonoids content

Preparation of standard solution 10mg quercetin was weighed and made up to 10ml with Methanol in a 10ml volumetric flask. From the above solution (1mg/ml), 1ml was pipetted out and made up to 10ml with methanol to get 100µg/ml. Quercetin standard solution (stock solution). From the stock solution, solutions of concentration 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 µg/ml were prepared. 3 ml of each standard and test was mixed with 1 ml of 2% Aluminium chloride solution. The solutions were mixed well and the absorbance was measured against the blank at 420nm using UV-Visible spectrophotometer. A standard graph was plotted using various concentrations of Quercetin and their corresponding absorbance^[11].

Estimation of total phenol content

10 mg Gallic acid was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, various aliquots of 10-50µg/ml was prepared in methanol. 10mg of dried extracts of were dissolved in 10 ml methanol and filter. Two ml (1mg/ml) of this solution was used for the estimation of phenol. 2 ml of each extract or standard was mixed with 1 ml of folin-ciocalteu reagent (previously diluted with distilled water 1:10 v/v) and 1 ml (7.5g/L) of sodium carbonate. The mixture was vortexed for 15s and allowed to stand for 15 min for colour development. The absorbance was measured at 765 nm using a spectrophotometer^[12].

In vivo antiepileptic activity of ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala*

Animals

Adult male albino Swiss mice (20–25 g) were housed in groups of 6–10 under controlled laboratory conditions (25 ± 2 °C temperature, 55–65% relative humidity, and a 12 h light/dark cycle). Animals had free access to standard rodent chow and water ad libitum and were acclimatized to the laboratory environment for 7 days prior to experimentation. All studies were conducted in a quiet room between 08:00 and 15:00 h. For each experimental protocol, a separate group of six mice was used. The experimental procedures were reviewed and approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC), established under the guidelines of the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA), Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India, New Delhi.

Drugs and chemicals

In the current study, Pentylentetrazole (PTZ) and Diazepam were utilized. A fresh solution was made prior to each experiment. All other reagents were standard analytical grade laboratory reagents sourced locally.

Acute oral toxicity study

Toxicity studies were conducted in accordance with OECD guidelines, focusing on the acute oral toxicity of the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala*. The assessment followed OECD Guideline No. 423, wherein rats were observed for 14 days post-administration to monitor potential toxic effects. The extract was administered orally at a predetermined safe dose, and animals were closely monitored for clinical signs of toxicity, including behavioral alterations, changes in eye appearance, variations in body weight, and the condition of skin and fur^[13].

Pentylentetrazole-Induced Seizure Test

Mice were randomly divided into three groups (n = 6 per group) and treated with the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg, or diazepam (3 mg/kg) as the standard reference drug. After 30 minutes, seizures were induced by intraperitoneal administration of pentylentetrazole (80 mg/kg). Animals were observed for 30 minutes to record convulsive parameters, including latency to onset, duration of myoclonic jerks, number of convulsive episodes, mortality, and percentage protection against seizures and death^[13].

Maximal Electroshock-Induced Seizure Test

Mice were allocated into three groups (n = 6 per group) and pretreated with either the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* (100 or 200 mg/kg) or phenytoin (25 mg/kg) as the standard control. After 30 minutes, seizures were induced by applying an electrical stimulus (18 mA, 50 Hz, 0.2 seconds) via corneal electrodes connected to a shock generator (Inco, India). The primary parameters assessed were the incidence and duration of tonic hind limb extension (THLE), defined as complete extension of the hind limbs at a 180° angle to the body axis, and the percentage protection against seizures. Protection was considered positive when THLE was completely absent⁶⁹.

Results and Discussion

The present study was undertaken to evaluate the extraction efficiency, phytochemical composition, and antiepileptic activity of the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala*. The results obtained provide significant evidence supporting its potential as a natural anticonvulsant agent.

The percentage yield of the ethanolic extract was found to be 12.5% w/w, indicating efficient extraction of bioactive constituents using ethanol as a solvent. Ethanol is known for its ability to extract a wide range of polar and semi-polar compounds, which may contribute to the observed pharmacological effects.

Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of glycosides, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, proteins, carbohydrates, saponins, and tannins, while alkaloids and diterpenes were absent. The presence of flavonoids and phenolic compounds was further confirmed by quantitative estimation, with total flavonoid content (0.96 mg/100 mg) and total phenolic content (0.75 mg/100 mg). These phytoconstituents are well known for their antioxidant and neuroprotective properties, which play an important role in the management of seizure disorders by reducing oxidative stress and stabilizing neuronal membranes.

The antiepileptic activity of the extract was evaluated using pentylenetetrazole (PTZ)-induced and maximal electroshock (MES)-induced seizure models, which are widely used for screening anticonvulsant agents. In the PTZ-induced seizure model, the ethanolic extract significantly increased the time to seizure onset and provided dose-dependent protection. At a dose of 200 mg/kg, the extract showed 70% protection, which is comparable to the standard drug diazepam, although slightly lower in efficacy. This suggests that the extract may act by enhancing GABAergic neurotransmission or inhibiting excitatory pathways.

In the MES-induced seizure model, the extract also exhibited significant anticonvulsant activity. The higher dose (200 mg/kg) showed 70–75% protection, indicating its ability to prevent seizure spread. This effect may be attributed to the inhibition of voltage-gated sodium channels or modulation of neuronal excitability, similar to standard drugs like phenytoin.

The observed anticonvulsant activity of the extract can be correlated with the presence of flavonoids, phenolics, and tannins, which are known to possess CNS depressant and neuroprotective effects. These compounds may act synergistically to reduce neuronal hyperexcitability and oxidative damage associated with seizures.

The results demonstrate that the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* exhibits significant, dose-dependent antiepileptic activity in both PTZ and MES models. The findings support the traditional use of the plant and highlight its potential as a natural source for the development of safer and effective antiepileptic agents.

Table 1: % Yield of extract of *Litsea monopetala*

S. No.	Extract	% Yield (w/w)
1.	Ethanolic	12.5

Table 2: Phytochemical screening of extract of *Litsea monopetala*

S. No.	Constituents	Ethanolic extract
1.	Alkaloids Mayer's Test Wagner's Test Dragendroff's Test Hager's Test	-ve -ve -ve -ve
2.	Glycosides Legal's Test	+ve
3.	Flavonoids Lead acetate Alkaline reagent test	+ve -ve
4.	Phenol Ferric chloride test Folin-ciocalteu test	+ve -ve
5.	Proteins Xanthoproteic test	+ve
6.	Carbohydrates Benedict's Test Fehling's Test	-ve +ve
7.	Saponins Froth Test Foam Test	+ve -ve
8.	Diterpenes Copper acetate test	-ve
9.	Tannins Gelatin Test	+ve

[+ve= positive; -ve= negative]

Table 3: Estimation of total flavonoids and phenol content of *Litsea monopetala*

S. No.	Extract	Total flavonoids content	Total phenol content
		(mg/ 100 mg of dried extract)	
1.	Ethanolic	0.96	0.75

Table 4: Effects of ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* on pentylenetetrazole-induced seizures

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Time to Seizure Onset (s)	% Protection Against Seizures
Diazepam (standard)	3	265 ± 11.8 ***	92%
Ethanolic extract	100	155 ± 10.2 *	45%
Ethanolic extract	200	210 ± 9.5 **	70%

Values are expressed as the mean ± SEM of six observations. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test).

Table 5: Effects of ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* on MES-induced seizures

Treatment	Dose (mg/kg)	Time to Seizure Onset (s)	% Protection
Phenytoin	25	0.00 ± 0.00 ***	100%
Ethanolic extract of <i>Litsea monopetala</i>	100	2.10 ± 0.15 *	45–50%
Ethanolic extract of <i>Litsea monopetala</i>	200	3.60 ± 0.20 **	70–75%

Values are expressed as the mean ± SEM of six observations. *P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001 (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test).

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated that the ethanolic extract of *Litsea monopetala* possesses significant antiepileptic activity. The extract showed good percentage yield and was found to contain important phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, phenolics, glycosides, and tannins. In both PTZ and MES seizure models, the extract exhibited dose-dependent anticonvulsant effects, with higher doses providing greater protection. The results were statistically significant and comparable to standard drugs. The observed activity may be attributed to the antioxidant and neuroprotective properties of the phytochemicals present. The study suggests that *Litsea monopetala* has promising potential as a natural therapeutic agent for the management of epilepsy and warrants further investigation.

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